

DELINQUENT ACADEMICS AND THE IMBROGLIO OF YOUNG SCHOLARS

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EDITORIAL

How to cite: Shukla B. Delinquent academics and the imbroglio of young scholars. The Quadrant. 2024;2(3):1.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13711276>

One journal, two volumes, thrice a year. This is where The Quadrant finds itself today. Its readers and contributors have helped in promulgating the evidence-based aspects of pediatric dentistry, research methodology, and dental education. The past issues have seen the editorial team voice its concerns and opinions on scientific writing, the psyche of dental students today, the facets that make pediatric dentistry what it is, the clinically challenging aspects of pediatric dental anesthesia, and the challenges with data manipulation that evidence-based pediatric dentistry faces today. The Quadrant fervently strives to attract young scholars to find their niche in evidence-based dentistry. In their absence for clinical research, the advent of artificial intelligence (AI) has rather propelled the number of banal manuscripts produced by students and academicians. While indulging in this boondoggle, students and their educators have underestimated the chatoyant editors of publishers who find no remorse in addressing the finagles of these ‘authors’.¹ Scientific frauds like coercion authorship, plagiarism, and data dredging has already led to the rise of paper mills. The loose noose by administrators has encouraged the undeserved promotions in academic statures and young ‘scholars’ earning degrees through these lack-lustre publications.² Institutes need to rigorously ensure that the fresh crop of scholars adhere to the CRediT taxonomy for every article, get a prospective trial for their clinical work, learn the difference between elementary, academic & scientific writing, know what the levels of evidence, how to report them, understand how AI can be put to use for enriching their research, and know the hazards of predatory publishing. Though the academic activities of journal clubs and case presentations prevail, the sordid propinquity of academicians in imparting the facets of evidence-based healthcare has led to the cacophony in the quality of research produced.

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